

LEXICAL AND SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF HYPONOMIC
RELATIONS IN ENGLISH LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: *This article describes the lexical and semantic relation of hyponyms in English linguistics, which means that analyzing deeply the features of hyponyms and its characteristic features. Hyponymy is considered the one of the most vital progresses in cognitive understanding of information, extremely significant devices to classifying vocabulary and performing of the human perception. Linguistic features of hyponyms are taken into consideration important when giving logical meaning and connection to speech that help to express the meaning of the word.*

Keywords: *hyponymy, hypero-hyponymic relation, lexical-semantic field, lexicon models, lexical unit.*

Introduction. In lexical classification, hyponymic relations of words, hierarchical structure of word combinations are considered important. Hyponymy is one of the types of systematic relations of units at the lexical-semantic level of language that is gender-type, reciprocal, hypero-hyponymic relations. According to giving different views about this relationship in the lexical system of language, we rely on the facts that hypero-hyponymic relationships confirmed by many studies which belong to universal connections of lexical units. The main relationship of

hyponymy is based on logical-semantic subordination that determines the hierarchical structure of individual semantic areas lexical layer of the language as a whole, structuring the lexicon of the language.

The 21st century has been called the “age of multilingualism” by the European Union, and the problem of effective learning and teaching of foreign languages is becoming increasingly important. In particular, raising the intellectual potential of young people in Uzbekistan, gaining a wide range of knowledge and professional skills, as well as active communication with peers abroad, keeping abreast of all events, innovations and changes in the world today, is the most important condition for acquiring great intellectual wealth. Great opportunities have been created for them to study foreign languages in depth. Like many other countries in the world, Uzbekistan pays special attention to the teaching and learning of foreign languages as a social direction of the state. There is every opportunity to keep abreast of the news [1] .

Literary review. Hyponymy is a less studied category in various systematic languages and has been considered in the scientific work of a number of researchers. The followings can be seen in the study of the problem of hyponymy in the work of scientists. To this time, many foreigners linguists investigated on many branches of language for instance, semantic and lexical characteristics of hyponymy that has been argued in their scientific research works which were illustrated many precious ideas and opinions. We can observe that the issue of hyponymy has been engaged in study about this in the works of the following linguists: Finch. G “Linguistic terms and concepts”, Firth J.R “Modes of meaning”, Cherry N “On Human Communication”, Bierwish B.M “ Semantics and Translations”, Palmer F.R “Semantics”, O’Grady W, Katamba F “Semantics and Pragmatics”, “The Analysis of Meaning” and Charles W.Kreidler “Introducing English Semantics”.

Research Methodology. The lexical units in this scheme are parts of the hyponymic or taxonomic paradigm. Given the probability that the tree structure is

in an asymmetric state, it can be observed that each lexical unit can have many hyponyms, but they have a single hyperonymy. For example, if the word “juice” has hyponyms such as “mandarin juice”, “Tropicana orange juice”, “navel orange juice”, “orange juice” is their hyperonymy. The word “fruit juice” is the hyperonymy of “orange juice”. According to English linguist Lyons, “these cross-categorical relations are quasi hyponymy. But even in nominal taxonomies, we see some differences in syntactic categories at the highest levels”[3]. Adjectives can also have nominal hyperonyms, for example “emotion>happy, sad, angry”. Hyponymy is a paradigmatic relationship in which the relationship between members of the same syntactic category is represented. The inter-category relationship is called “quasi-hyponymy”. In some cases, a high degree of syntactic category differences is observed in nominal taxonomy. For example, even though the word “*fruit*” in the picture above is a noun phrase, it is used in the adjective form “*fruit juice*”. The orange juice varieties “*navel*” and “*mandarin juice*” are represented at the bottom. Despite the fact that the words “*herbal juice*” and “*vegetable juice*” in the primary stage are in the unit of uncounted, the word “*juice*” is a noun in the category that is also not counted.

Figure 3.Hyponymic relationship in lexical field “**Juice**”

Conclusion. The hyponym and hyperonym relationship is very important in giving a logical connection in speech, expressing the meaning of words. There is no clear basis for the fact that a hypero-hyponomic relationship is a linguistic-

lexical relationship rather than a cognitive-semantic relationship. The taxonomies of hyponymy do not cover all types of relationships that fall into the general term. The fact that functional hyponyms do not have to be part of hyperonyms, the range of what is considered a hyponym in these taxonomies, suggests that hyponymy is a broad concept. English linguist A. Wierzbicka distinguishes hyponymic relations based on the morpho-semantic properties of hyperonyms. These ideas raise the question of the relationship between hyponymy and words or concepts or meanings[4].

Easy and quick teaching of various terms to young people in teaching English can increase the level of communication in this foreign language and allow them to freely express their opinions in a foreign language.

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